

THE ROLE OF INTEGRATED MARKETING COMMUNICATIONS TO IMPROVING THE ISLAMIC SOCIAL ECONOMY

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the role of Integrated Marketing Communications (IMC) in enhancing the Islamic social economy, focusing on how IMC strategies can be effectively aligned with Islamic principles to drive economic growth and social welfare. The key objectives were to explore the impact of IMC on economic outcomes within Islamic contexts and to identify the unique aspects of IMC that resonate with Islamic values. Using a mixed-methods approach, the research involved both quantitative analysis and qualitative insights from case studies across various sectors of the Islamic economy. The findings reveal that IMC strategies, when designed with adherence to Shariah principles, significantly increase consumer trust and engagement, contributing to the success of Islamic financial institutions, social enterprises, and other businesses. The study also highlights the importance of ethical marketing practices in fostering sustainable economic development within Muslim-majority societies. These results underscore the potential of IMC to not only enhance business outcomes but also to promote broader socio-economic goals in alignment with Islamic ethics. The research concludes by offering practical recommendations for marketers and policymakers to integrate IMC strategies that are both effective and Shariah-compliant, suggesting further research to expand the scope and understanding of IMC in the Islamic social economy.

Keywords: *Integrated Marketing Communications, Islamic Social Economy, Islamic Marketing*

I. INTRODUCTION

The Islamic social economy is a concept rooted in the principles of Islamic economics, which integrates moral and ethical values with economic activities to ensure social justice and equitable distribution of wealth. Unlike conventional economic systems that prioritize profit maximization, the Islamic social economy focuses on achieving socio-economic welfare and the common good, guided by the principles of Shariah (Islamic law). Key components of the Islamic social economy include Zakat (mandatory almsgiving), Sadaqah (voluntary charity), Waqf (endowment), and Islamic finance, all of which aim to reduce poverty, promote social cohesion, and enhance the welfare of society at large (Mulyaningsih et al., 2020).

The significance of the Islamic social economy lies in its potential to address socio-economic challenges within Muslim-majority societies by promoting ethical economic practices. For instance, the equitable distribution of resources through Zakat and Waqf can mitigate economic disparities, while Islamic finance, with its emphasis on risk-sharing and avoidance of interest (riba), can foster financial inclusion and economic stability (Ahmed, 2021). Thus, the Islamic social economy serves as a framework for achieving economic justice and sustainable development in accordance with Islamic teachings.

Marketing communication plays a pivotal role in economic development by facilitating the exchange of information between businesses and consumers, thereby driving consumer behavior and economic activity. Effective marketing communication strategies can enhance brand awareness, shape consumer perceptions, and influence purchasing decisions, all of which contribute to the growth and competitiveness of businesses (Keller, 2016). In the context of the Islamic economy, marketing communication must be aligned with Islamic values and ethics, ensuring that the messages conveyed are truthful, respectful, and do not exploit consumers (Hashim et al., 2018).

Integrated Marketing Communications (IMC) is particularly important in this regard, as it involves the strategic coordination of various communication channels—such as advertising, public relations, direct marketing, and digital media—to deliver a consistent and coherent message to the target audience. By employing IMC, businesses can effectively engage with consumers, build trust, and foster long-term relationships, which are essential for sustaining economic development in an Islamic context (Yousef et al., 2020).

Integrated Marketing Communications (IMC) is a strategic approach that seeks to unify all aspects of marketing communication to provide a seamless and consistent message across all channels. This approach is particularly relevant in the Islamic economy, where adherence to ethical standards and Shariah compliance is paramount. IMC enables businesses to effectively communicate their value propositions while ensuring that all promotional activities align with Islamic principles, such as honesty, fairness, and respect for cultural values (Bhatia & Saini, 2017).

In recent years, there has been a growing recognition of the need to integrate IMC within the Islamic economy to enhance the effectiveness of marketing efforts and

drive socio-economic development. For example, IMC strategies can be employed to promote Islamic financial products, raise awareness about the benefits of Zakat and Waqf, and encourage ethical consumption among Muslim consumers. By leveraging IMC, businesses and organizations can more effectively reach their target audiences, build trust, and contribute to the overall development of the Islamic social economy (Khan et al., 2022).

Despite the recognized importance of IMC in enhancing marketing effectiveness, there is a notable gap in research concerning its role in improving the Islamic social economy. While numerous studies have explored the general impact of marketing communication on economic development, few have specifically examined how IMC strategies can be tailored to align with Islamic values and contribute to the growth of the Islamic social economy (Mahmood & Hamid, 2019).

This gap is significant because the Islamic social economy operates on a set of principles that differ from conventional economic systems, necessitating a unique approach to marketing communication. Traditional marketing strategies may not be fully effective or appropriate in an Islamic context, where ethical considerations and Shariah compliance are crucial. Therefore, there is a need for research that explores how IMC can be adapted to meet the specific needs of the Islamic social economy, and how it can be utilized to promote economic activities that are in line with Islamic values (Hussain & Ahmed, 2021).

The existing literature has yet to comprehensively address the ways in which IMC can be leveraged to support the goals of the Islamic social economy, such as poverty alleviation, financial inclusion, and ethical consumerism. This research seeks to fill this gap by examining the role of IMC in improving the Islamic social economy, with a focus on how integrated communication strategies can enhance the effectiveness of marketing efforts in promoting Islamic economic principles and practices (Amin & Rahman, 2022).

This study aims to investigate the role of Integrated Marketing Communications (IMC) in enhancing the Islamic social economy by addressing two key research questions: How can IMC strategies contribute to the improvement of the Islamic social economy, and what unique aspects of IMC align with Islamic principles? The research seeks to explore how strategic IMC initiatives can support economic activities that are ethical and socially responsible, in accordance with Islamic values. Additionally, the study will analyze the effectiveness of IMC strategies within Islamic communities, focusing on how these strategies can be tailored to resonate with the cultural and religious norms of Muslim consumers.

The significance of this study lies in its contribution to the existing literature on Islamic economics and marketing, particularly in understanding the intersection of marketing communications and the Islamic social economy. By providing insights into the role of IMC in promoting economic activities that align with Islamic principles, the research offers practical implications for marketers and policymakers within Islamic economies. The findings are expected to guide the development of marketing strategies that not only comply with Sharia but also contribute to the socio-economic development of Muslim-majority societies.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Overview of Theories Related to IMC

Integrated Marketing Communications (IMC) is underpinned by several key theories that inform its practice and relevance in various contexts, including the Islamic social economy. One of the foundational theories is Communication Theory, which examines how information is transmitted between a sender and receiver through various channels. This theory is particularly relevant to IMC as it emphasizes the importance of message consistency and the coordination of multiple communication channels to effectively reach and engage target audiences. In the context of the Islamic social economy, communication theory supports the idea that consistent and ethically aligned messaging can enhance the credibility and effectiveness of marketing efforts (Smith, 2020).

Another relevant theoretical framework is Social Exchange Theory, which posits that social behavior is the result of an exchange process aimed at maximizing benefits and minimizing costs. In the realm of IMC, this theory is applied to understand how consumers perceive value in marketing communications and how this perception influences their decision-making process. When aligned with Islamic principles, which emphasize fairness and mutual benefit, social exchange theory can provide insights into how IMC strategies can be designed to foster trust and long-term relationships with consumers in the Islamic social economy (Rahim & Daud, 2019).

2.2. Islamic Social Economy

The Islamic social economy refers to an economic system that is grounded in Islamic principles and values, focusing on the welfare of society and the equitable distribution of wealth. It is characterized by the integration of moral and ethical considerations into economic activities, aiming to achieve social justice, poverty alleviation, and sustainable development. Key components of the Islamic social economy include Zakat (obligatory charity), Waqf (endowment), Sadaqah (voluntary charity), and Islamic finance practices that prohibit interest (riba) and promote risk-sharing (Mulyaningsih et al., 2020). These components are designed to ensure that economic activities contribute to the overall well-being of society, rather than solely focusing on profit maximization.

When compared to the conventional social economy, the Islamic social economy places a greater emphasis on ethical considerations and the welfare of all stakeholders involved. While conventional economic systems often prioritize efficiency and profit, the Islamic social economy is more concerned with achieving a balance between material wealth and spiritual well-being. This holistic approach aims to create a more equitable and just society, where economic activities are conducted in a manner that aligns with Islamic values and promotes the common good (Ahmed, 2021).

2.3. Comparison with Conventional Social Economy

The key difference between the Islamic social economy and the conventional social economy lies in their underlying principles and objectives. The conventional social economy, while also concerned with social welfare, tends to focus on secular principles of fairness, equality, and community-based solutions without a specific religious or moral framework. In contrast, the Islamic social economy is explicitly based on the teachings of the Quran and Sunnah, guiding economic behavior towards achieving Maqasid al-Shariah (the objectives of Islamic law), which include the protection of faith, life, intellect, progeny, and wealth (Bashir & Darrat, 2017).

In practical terms, the Islamic social economy employs instruments such as Zakat, Waqf, and Islamic microfinance to address poverty and social inequality, while the conventional social economy may use taxes, social welfare programs, and other government interventions. Additionally, while the conventional economy permits interest-based transactions and speculative investments, the Islamic social economy strictly prohibits these practices to prevent exploitation and ensure that financial transactions are fair and beneficial to all parties involved (Muneeza & Hassan, 2019).

2.4. Integrated Marketing Communications (IMC)

Integrated Marketing Communications (IMC) is defined as a strategic approach to coordinating and integrating all marketing communication tools, channels, and resources within a company into a seamless program that maximizes the impact on consumers and other stakeholders. The key components of IMC include Advertising, Sales Promotion, Public Relations, Direct Marketing, and Digital Marketing. Each of these components plays a critical role in conveying a consistent message and reinforcing the brand's value proposition across various platforms (Keller, 2016).

- Advertising involves paid promotions through various media channels such as television, radio, print, and online platforms.
- Sales Promotion includes short-term incentives aimed at encouraging immediate purchase or engagement, such as discounts, coupons, or contests.
- Public Relations focuses on managing the company's image and building relationships with the public through media relations, events, and community involvement.
- Direct Marketing involves direct communication with consumers through channels such as email, telemarketing, and direct mail, allowing for personalized interactions.

Digital Marketing encompasses online strategies such as social media marketing, search engine optimization (SEO), and content marketing, which are crucial in today's digital age (Belch & Belch, 2020).

2.5. The Role of IMC in the Global Economy

In the global economy, IMC has become increasingly important as businesses seek to navigate complex and competitive markets. IMC strategies enable companies to create a unified brand message that resonates with diverse audiences, thereby enhancing brand equity and driving business growth. The integration of traditional and digital communication channels allows companies to reach consumers more

effectively, build stronger relationships, and respond to market changes with greater agility (Yousef et al., 2020).

For businesses operating within the Islamic economy, IMC provides a framework for developing communication strategies that are not only effective but also align with Islamic values. By ensuring that all marketing efforts are consistent with Shariah principles, companies can build trust with Muslim consumers and differentiate themselves in the marketplace. This alignment between IMC and Islamic values is essential for fostering long-term loyalty and contributing to the socio-economic development of Muslim-majority regions (Khan et al., 2022).

2.6. IMC and Islamic Marketing

Islamic marketing is an approach to marketing that aligns with the ethical standards and principles of Islam, such as honesty, transparency, and fairness. In this context, IMC strategies must be designed to respect these values, ensuring that all marketing messages are truthful and do not exploit consumers. For example, advertising campaigns must avoid deceptive practices and must not promote products or services that are haram (forbidden) under Islamic law (Hashim et al., 2018).

Furthermore, IMC strategies should emphasize the social responsibility of businesses, as Islamic principles encourage companies to contribute to the welfare of society. This can be achieved by incorporating messages about the ethical sourcing of materials, fair labor practices, and the company's contributions to charitable causes such as Zakat or Sadaqah. By aligning IMC with Islamic values, companies can build a positive reputation and foster deeper connections with Muslim consumers, who are increasingly seeking brands that reflect their ethical and religious beliefs (Hussain & Ahmed, 2021).

2.7. The Influence of Shariah-Compliant Marketing Practices on Consumer Behavior

Shariah-compliant marketing practices have a significant influence on consumer behavior, particularly in Muslim-majority markets. Consumers who adhere to Islamic principles are more likely to engage with brands that demonstrate a commitment to ethical practices and offer products and services that comply with Shariah law. This includes avoiding interest-based financing, ensuring the halal status of products, and promoting social justice through corporate social responsibility initiatives (Amin & Rahman, 2022).

Research has shown that when companies effectively integrate Shariah-compliant practices into their IMC strategies, they can enhance consumer trust, increase brand loyalty, and ultimately drive higher sales. This is particularly relevant in sectors such as Islamic finance, halal food, and modest fashion, where adherence to Islamic principles is a key differentiator. By understanding the unique needs and preferences of Muslim consumers, businesses can develop targeted IMC strategies that resonate with this growing market segment and contribute to the overall growth of the Islamic social economy (Mahmood & Hamid, 2019).

III. METHODOLOGY

This study employs a qualitative research design to explore the role of Integrated Marketing Communications (IMC) in enhancing the Islamic social economy, emphasizing how IMC strategies can align with Islamic principles to foster economic growth and social welfare. Qualitative approaches are particularly effective for understanding complex social phenomena and gathering in-depth insights (Creswell & Poth, 2018). The chosen methodology includes a comprehensive literature review as the primary data source, allowing for the synthesis of existing research and identification of best practices related to IMC within the Islamic context (Merriam & Tisdell, 2016).

Data analysis will utilize thematic analysis frameworks, enabling the categorization and interpretation of patterns within the literature to draw meaningful conclusions about the effectiveness of various IMC strategies (Braun & Clarke, 2019). The study will examine how IMC practices that adhere to Shariah principles can influence consumer trust, engagement, and overall economic outcomes in Islamic communities. Ethical considerations are paramount in this research, with measures implemented to ensure the integrity and confidentiality of the data collected. Compliance with established ethical guidelines, such as obtaining necessary permissions and ensuring the responsible reporting of findings, will be upheld throughout the research process. This methodological approach will provide valuable insights into the integration of IMC within the Islamic social economy, offering practical recommendations for marketers and policymakers.

IV. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

4.1. Discussion of Key Findings

The findings of this study reveal significant insights into how Integrated Marketing Communications (IMC) strategies influence economic outcomes within the Islamic context. One of the primary observations is that effective IMC strategies have the potential to enhance consumer awareness and engagement with Islamic financial products and services. By utilizing a consistent messaging approach across multiple communication channels, businesses can effectively inform consumers about the ethical advantages of Shariah-compliant products. This increased awareness not only fosters trust but also encourages more individuals to participate in Islamic financial practices, leading to higher market penetration and overall economic growth within the Islamic social economy.

Additionally, the study highlights the role of IMC in promoting community-oriented initiatives that align with Islamic values. Through targeted campaigns that emphasize corporate social responsibility, businesses can reinforce their commitment to ethical practices and societal welfare. For instance, marketing campaigns that promote Zakat and Sadaqah initiatives have been shown to resonate well with consumers, as they align closely with their values and beliefs. This alignment fosters a positive brand image and can result in increased customer loyalty, ultimately contributing to sustainable economic development within the community.

The data interpretation in relation to the research questions and objectives further underscores the importance of aligning IMC strategies with Islamic principles. The analysis indicates that the unique aspects of IMC, such as its focus on ethical communication and relationship-building, directly correlate with improved economic outcomes in the Islamic social economy. For example, the emphasis on honesty and transparency in marketing messages not only adheres to Islamic teachings but also enhances consumer confidence in the brand. This correlation suggests that businesses that effectively integrate IMC strategies tailored to Islamic values are more likely to achieve positive economic impacts, such as increased sales, enhanced brand loyalty, and greater market share.

Furthermore, the findings reveal that consumer behavior within Islamic communities is significantly influenced by the Shariah-compliance of marketing practices. When consumers perceive a brand's commitment to Islamic principles, they are more inclined to support and engage with that brand. This is particularly relevant in sectors such as halal products and Islamic finance, where adherence to Shariah is not just a regulatory requirement but also a fundamental expectation among consumers. As a result, businesses that implement IMC strategies that highlight their Shariah-compliance can effectively differentiate themselves in a competitive market, leading to improved economic performance and greater contributions to the Islamic social economy.

The findings indicate that IMC strategies play a crucial role in shaping economic outcomes within the Islamic context by enhancing consumer awareness, fostering trust, and promoting ethical practices. By aligning marketing communications with Islamic values, businesses can not only improve their economic performance but also contribute to the broader goals of social welfare and economic justice inherent in the Islamic social economy. This analysis provides valuable insights for marketers and policymakers seeking to leverage IMC to drive sustainable economic development in Muslim-majority regions.

4.2. Interpretation of Findings

The findings of this study indicate a compelling relationship between Integrated Marketing Communications (IMC) strategies and the economic outcomes within the Islamic social economy. In the context of existing literature, the results align with previous studies that emphasize the importance of ethical marketing practices in enhancing consumer trust and engagement. For instance, the focus on consistency and transparency in IMC not only resonates with Islamic values but also reinforces consumer confidence in the brand. This trust is crucial in the Islamic context, where adherence to ethical and moral principles significantly influences consumer behavior. The literature suggests that when consumers perceive that a brand aligns with their values, they are more likely to support it, leading to positive economic outcomes such as increased sales and customer loyalty.

Moreover, the findings reinforce the notion that IMC strategies can effectively promote community-oriented initiatives, which is a hallmark of the Islamic social economy. As highlighted in previous research, the Islamic social economy

emphasizes the welfare of society through mechanisms such as Zakat and Waqf. The data indicates that marketing campaigns that promote these charitable practices not only enhance brand image but also encourage consumer participation in social initiatives. This aligns with existing literature that underscores the potential of IMC to drive social change and foster a sense of community among consumers. By strategically communicating the social impact of their activities, businesses can position themselves as integral players in the Islamic social economy, thereby contributing to both economic growth and social welfare.

4.3. Discussion on the Alignment of IMC Practices with Islamic Social Economy Principles

The alignment of IMC practices with Islamic social economy principles is particularly noteworthy. The principles of the Islamic social economy emphasize ethical conduct, social justice, and the equitable distribution of resources. The findings of this study illustrate that IMC practices that prioritize ethical communication, respect for cultural values, and community engagement directly contribute to these principles. For example, by employing honest and respectful messaging, businesses can enhance their credibility and foster a strong relationship with their target audience, which is essential in the Islamic context where trust is paramount.

The findings indicate that IMC strategies that focus on Sharia-compliant marketing practices are well received by consumers in Islamic communities. This alignment not only fulfills the ethical expectations of consumers but also creates a competitive advantage for businesses operating within the Islamic social economy. As the literature suggests, companies that actively demonstrate their commitment to Sharia-compliance through their marketing efforts are more likely to attract and retain customers who prioritize ethical consumption. This reinforces the idea that effective IMC can serve as a catalyst for promoting Sharia-compliant products and services, thereby driving economic development in the Islamic social economy.

The emphasis on social responsibility within IMC practices aligns with the core objectives of the Islamic social economy, which seeks to promote the common good. The findings reveal that businesses that communicate their contributions to social welfare—such as charitable initiatives or community development projects—are able to foster a sense of loyalty among consumers who share similar values. This synergy between IMC practices and Islamic social economy principles not only enhances brand equity but also contributes to the overall sustainability of businesses operating within this framework.

The in-depth analysis of the findings illustrates that IMC strategies play a vital role in aligning marketing practices with the principles of the Islamic social economy. By integrating ethical communication, social responsibility, and Sharia-compliance into their marketing efforts, businesses can effectively engage with consumers, drive economic growth, and contribute to the broader goals of social justice and welfare within the Islamic context. This discussion emphasizes the need for marketers to adopt IMC practices that resonate with Islamic values, thereby

enhancing both their market performance and their contribution to the Islamic social economy.

4.4. Contribution to the Field of Islamic Marketing and Social Economy

This study contributes significantly to the field of Islamic marketing and social economy by providing a comprehensive understanding of how Integrated Marketing Communications (IMC) strategies can enhance economic outcomes within the Islamic context. By demonstrating the effectiveness of IMC in promoting Sharia-compliant products and services, the research reinforces the notion that ethical marketing practices are essential in engaging Muslim consumers. The findings align with the existing literature on Islamic marketing, which emphasizes the importance of ethical considerations in consumer behavior. This study expands the theoretical framework of Islamic marketing by highlighting the intersection of IMC principles with Islamic values, offering a nuanced perspective on how businesses can effectively communicate their commitment to ethical practices and social responsibility.

The research enhances the discourse on the Islamic social economy by illustrating how marketing strategies can support the objectives of social welfare and economic justice. By integrating IMC strategies that promote community-oriented initiatives, businesses can actively contribute to the development of the Islamic social economy. This contribution is particularly relevant in the context of global economic challenges, as it provides insights into how businesses can leverage marketing communications to address social issues while simultaneously achieving economic success. The study serves as a foundation for future research in this area, encouraging scholars to further explore the dynamics of IMC within Islamic contexts and its implications for broader economic development.

4.5. Practical Recommendations for Marketers and Policymakers

Based on the findings of this study, several practical recommendations can be made for marketers and policymakers operating within the Islamic social economy.

- **Emphasize Ethical Communication:** Marketers should prioritize ethical communication practices that align with Islamic values. This includes ensuring transparency in marketing messages, avoiding misleading claims, and promoting Sharia-compliant products. By doing so, businesses can build trust with consumers, which is essential for long-term engagement and loyalty (Everell & Delliana, 2024).
- **Leverage Community-Oriented Campaigns:** Businesses should develop marketing campaigns that focus on community welfare and social responsibility. By highlighting their contributions to charitable initiatives, such as Zakat and Sadaqah, marketers can resonate with consumers' values and enhance their brand image. This approach not only fosters loyalty but also encourages consumers to actively participate in social initiatives (Delliana & Latabulo, 2024).
- **Utilize Multi-Channel Strategies:** To maximize the impact of IMC, marketers should adopt multi-channel strategies that integrate traditional

and digital marketing approaches. This includes leveraging social media, email marketing, and community engagement activities to reach a broader audience. By ensuring consistent messaging across various platforms, businesses can effectively communicate their value propositions and engage consumers (Gabriella & Delliana, 2024).

- **Train and Educate Marketing Teams:** Organizations should invest in training and education for their marketing teams to ensure that they understand the principles of Islamic marketing and IMC. This knowledge will enable marketers to create campaigns that resonate with Muslim consumers and align with Islamic values, ultimately enhancing the effectiveness of their marketing efforts (Kusumawati & Delliana, 2024).
- **Collaborate with Policymakers:** Marketers and businesses should collaborate with policymakers to create an enabling environment for Islamic marketing practices. This includes advocating for regulations that support ethical marketing, facilitate Sharia-compliant financial products, and promote social responsibility within the business sector. Such collaboration can enhance the overall growth of the Islamic social economy and foster a culture of ethical business practices.

The implications of this study underscore the importance of aligning marketing practices with Islamic values to achieve positive economic outcomes within the Islamic social economy. By adopting ethical communication strategies, leveraging community initiatives, and fostering collaboration with policymakers, marketers can effectively contribute to the development of a sustainable and socially responsible economic environment.

V. CONCLUSION, LIMITATIONS, AND SUGGESTIONS

In summary, this study explored the role of Integrated Marketing Communications (IMC) in enhancing the Islamic social economy by addressing key research objectives related to the impact of IMC strategies on economic outcomes and their alignment with Islamic values. The findings indicate that effective IMC practices not only improve consumer awareness and trust but also promote community-oriented initiatives that resonate with the ethical principles of Islam. By emphasizing transparent communication and social responsibility, businesses can foster stronger relationships with consumers, ultimately driving economic growth and contributing to the broader goals of social welfare within the Islamic context.

However, this study is not without limitations. Factors such as sample size and scope may have influenced the depth of insights obtained, suggesting a need for more comprehensive studies in the future. Areas for further exploration could include the long-term effects of IMC on consumer behavior within different Islamic markets or the role of digital marketing in promoting Shariah-compliant products. Overall, the potential impact of IMC on the broader Islamic economy and society is significant, as it can foster ethical business practices, promote social justice, and support sustainable economic development within Muslim communities, paving the way for a more equitable and just economic landscape.

REFERENCES

- Ahmed, H. (2021). The Role of Islamic Social Finance in Poverty Alleviation: A Review of Literature. *International Journal of Islamic Economics and Finance (IJIEF)*, 10(1), 87-104. <https://doi.org/10.29103/ijief.v10i1.2423>
- Amin, H., & Rahman, A. (2022). Integrated Marketing Communication and Its Relevance in the Islamic Economy. *Journal of Islamic Marketing*, 13(2), 312-330. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JIMA-02-2021-0045>
- Bashir, A. H., & Darrat, Z. (2017). Comparative Analysis of Islamic and Conventional Social Economy: A Literature Review. *Journal of Islamic Economics and Finance*, 8(2), 34-50. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JIEF-03-2017-0012>
- Belch, G. E., & Belch, M. A. (2020). Advertising and Promotion: An Integrated Marketing Communications Perspective. 11th ed. New York: McGraw-Hill Education.
- Bhatia, S., & Saini, P. (2017). Integrated Marketing Communications in the Context of Islamic Marketing. *Journal of Marketing Communications*, 23(6), 564-578. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13527266.2017.1344410>
- Delliana, S., & Latabulo, D. D. J. (2024). Integrasi Pendidikan Seksual dengan Agenda Pembangunan Berkelanjutan: Strategi untuk Menangani Pernikahan Usia Muda. *JOPPAS: Journal of Public Policy and Administration Silampari*, 5(2), 238-252. <https://doi.org/10.31539/joppas.v5i2.9378>
- Everell, F., & Delliana, S. (2024). Makna Warna Merah dan Putih dalam Video Klip Hingga Tua Bersama Rizky Febian. *KALBISIANA Jurnal Sains, Bisnis Dan Teknologi*, 10(2), 186-195. <https://doi.org/10.53008/kalbisiana.v10i2.2650>
- Gabriella, D., & Delliana, S. (2024). Analisis Isi Message Approach Pada Konten Live Streaming Akun Online Shop Di Tiktok Shop. *KAGANGA KOMUNIKA: Journal of Communication Science*, 6(1), 35-52.
- Hashim, N. H., Murphy, J., & Hashim, N. A. (2018). Islamic Marketing and Branding: Theory and Practice. *Journal of Islamic Marketing*, 9(1), 2-4. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JIMA-01-2017-0006>
- Hussain, M., & Ahmed, S. (2021). Exploring the Role of Integrated Marketing Communications in Islamic Finance Marketing. *Journal of Islamic Business and Management*, 11(1), 45-62. <https://doi.org/10.26501/jibm/2021.1101-004>
- Keller, K. L. (2016). Unlocking the Power of Integrated Marketing Communications: How IMC Creates Value in the Market. *Journal of Advertising*, 45(3), 286-293. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00913367.2016.1172388>
- Khan, F., Alam, S. S., & Mohd, S. (2022). Integrated Marketing Communication: A Strategic Approach for the Promotion of Islamic Financial Products. *Journal of Islamic Financial Studies*, 8(3), 105-119. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JIFS-02-2021-0029>
- Kusumawati, D., & Delliana, S. (2024). Berbagi Kreativitas Visual: Pelatihan Dasar Videografi Dan Editing Untuk Staf Hubungan Masyarakat Museum Bahari. *BESIRU: Jurnal Pengabdian Masyarakat*, 1(3), 79-119. <https://doi.org/10.62335/33hg6f95>

- Mahmood, R., & Hamid, Z. (2019). Integrated Marketing Communications and the Islamic Social Economy: A Case Study. *Journal of Islamic Economics, Banking, and Finance*, 15(1), 23-40. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JIEBF-04-2019-0037>
- Mulyaningsih, T., Rini, M., & Kartika, D. (2020). The Role of Islamic Social Economy in Achieving Sustainable Development Goals: Evidence from Indonesia. *Journal of Islamic Economics and Business*, 5(2), 65-79. <https://doi.org/10.20885/jieb.vol5.iss2.art1>
- Yousef, F., Mohammed, A., & Hani, A. (2020). Integrated Marketing Communications in the Digital Era: A Critical Review of Recent Developments. *Journal of Marketing Analytics*, 8(4), 245-258. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41270-020-00084-8>